

WLT[®] Wave Layered Timber

Glue-free mass timber for aesthetic structures

This innovative construction technology from Finland focusses on simplicity and flexibility: the concept is a universal mass timber building component for every type of construction that can be manufactured with basic technical skills using different types of wood.

Highlights of innovative features

- This special wave profile joining technique creates homogenous, crack-free tight structures with high dimensional strength. The material reacts to ambient moisture changes by natural optimisation of tensions. It suits various wood species, including recycled wood.

- It is a highly versatile, cost-efficient building system: The structurally strong, light-weight material enables demanding structural shapes.
- It has a short lead, production and construction time.
- It can easily be modified, disassembled and transported for re-use.
- It is glue and additive free and thus ecologically harmless, fully recyclable with zero waste.

WLT[®] makes practical and beautiful solutions possible even under demanding conditions or logistical restrictions. The assembly demands little training and no special equipment.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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